

Employee empowerment and organizational citizenship behaviour

 Vanjesryl G. Calaycay^(c)

 Fredolin P. Julian^(e)

^(a,e) Professor(s), School of Business and Accountancy, Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte, Philippines

^(b) EdD., President, Saint Benedict College of the Northern Luzon, Ilocos Sur, Philippines

^(c,d) MAN, Instructor(s), School of Nursing, Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte, Philippines.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 10 November 2021

Received in rev. form 01 Dec. 2021

Accepted 02 December 2021

Keywords:

Empowerment, organizational citizenship, the delegation of authority, autonomy, self-efficacy self-management.

JEL Classification:

O15

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to find out the effect of employee empowerment practices on the organizational citizenship behaviors of employees toward the organization and toward their coworkers (OCBP & OCBO). To support and establish the theory of the study, literature was reviewed. The study used the descriptive correlational research design and it used the questionnaires to gather the data. The study found that the empowerment practices of the Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of delegation of authority, autonomy, and self-efficacy self-management is high and even the different dimensions of organizational citizenship behavior are also high but not very high. Concerning the relationship between empowerment practices and organizational citizenship behavior of employees, the study was found to be significantly correlated. Therefore, the hypothesis of this study is accepted.

© 2021 by the authors. Licensee Bussecon International, Istanbul, Turkey. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC BY) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

Organizations have been experiencing difficulties dealing with a lot of situations. It faces financial difficulties, competition, technology, environmental uncertainties, market uncertainties caused by the pandemic. One can imagine how the managers can sleep well at night when they are surrounded by so many problems. Managers are overwhelmed by these problems and these challenges cannot be dealt with by a single man alone. Human capabilities are limited and therefore, synergy is needed to deal with all kinds of these problems. Facing all these kinds of problems alone would be difficult and can develop psychosomatic illnesses. All these problems cause headaches and can lead to bankruptcy if not handled properly.

Those are the challenges that are facing the managers and employees as well at this time. Leadership is challenged on how to keep the organizations survive and continue to grow. Their concern is how to prevent those situations from damaging the organization. This is the concern of all those who are working for the organization. It is not only the responsibility of managers to prevent the organization from bankruptcy but it is the responsibility of all those who are involved in the operation. Thus, the key to survival is not only about financial capital but it is about human capital. Managing well human resources is a tough job for the management. Managing human resources is not only about the salaries and benefits but also the working environment. The working environment must be conducive where employees can release their hidden talents and energy to perform their job. Thus, it is important to establish trust working environment where employers trust their employees and employees trust each other and the management. A distrust working environment demotivates employees to perform. It affects employees' behavior, interaction, and the establishment of workplace relationships (Herselman, 2003). Thielsch, et.al (2018) agree with such a finding, that trust and distrust affect the well-being and performance of employees. Thus, motivating employees to perform is not only about money but it is also about the morale

* Corresponding author. ORCID ID:0000-0002-9693-1541

© 2021 by the authors. Hosting by Bussecon International Academy. Peer review under responsibility of Bussecon International Academy.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.36096/ijbes.v3i3.267>

of employees. Improving the morale of employees cannot be done through financial recognition but it can be done through empowerment. Empowerment is trust given to the employees to perform their job on their own. Employees are the ones to decide how to carry out their duties and responsibilities. Lee, et.al (2018) contended that empowerment results in job performance, job performance, and commitment to the organization.

The researcher has been working with the Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Region for 25 years and has been occupying different positions such as Vice President for Administration, Vice President for Finance, Head of Human Resources, Head of Quality Assurance and Accreditation, Head for Research Centre and also experience as an ordinary faculty. The researcher knows very well what it means and feels to be in the position, to lead and to be led by other people, and knows what it means to be an ordinary employee. From those experiences, the researcher knows what it means to be empowered and disempowered. The researcher knows what it means to be powerless and subject to the dictate of others. In the same way, the employees know what it means to be empowered and disempowered.

There have been many studies related to organizational trust and job satisfaction, commitment and work engagement such as Callaway, et.al (2007), Fard and Karimi (2015), Gucer and Demirdag (2014), Gider, et.al (2019), Celep and Yilmazturk (2012), Ugwu, et.al (2014), however, there have been no studies yet along with employee empowerment and organizational citizenship behavior. Thus, the current study would like to fill the gap. The current study aims at determining the level of empowerment of employees as a result of trust and how it affects their organizational citizenship behavior. The purpose of the study is to provide feedback to the management to revisit their leadership styles to improve the working environment by entrusting employees more. Employees are the key to organizational success and therefore the employees should be given the autonomy to perform their job on their own by giving them the power to decide.

The paper aims to determine the effect of employee empowerment and organizational citizenship behavior of employees of Divine Word College of Laoag in Ilocos Norte. It specifically seeks to answer the following questions:

- i. What is the employee empowerment of Divine Word College of Laoag in the Ilocos Norte in terms of:
 - a. Delegation of authority
 - b. Autonomy/Independence
 - c. Self-Efficacy-Self-Management
- ii. What is the organizational citizenship behavior of employees in terms of
 - a. OCBP
 - b. OCBO
- iii. Is there a relationship between empowerment practices and organizational citizenship behavior of the employees?

The study assumes that empowerment affects the organizational citizenship behavior of the employees and it can be measured.

The scope of the study is only the employees of Divine Word College of Laoag in Ilocos Norte, and it limits its discussion on empowerment specifically on the delegation of authority and self-efficacy practices and its effect on the organizational citizenship behavior particularly to the organization and co-workers.

The study is divided into several parts. The first part is the introduction that explains the rationale of the study. The second part is the literature review which finds out related literature that supports the theories of the current study. The third part is the research methodology that presents the research design, population, locale, research instrument, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data. The fourth part is the presentation of data and analysis. This part presents the data in the tables and is followed by the interpretation or analysis. The fifth part is the result and discussion which discusses further the result and the implication of the study.

Literature Review

This part presents a comprehensive summary of the previous researches related to the current topic. The purpose is to establish theories of the current study. These reviews will be arranged thematically according to the theories of the current study.

Theoretical and Conceptual Background

Empowerment

It has to be recognized that there has been no consensus among researchers about the definition and practices of empowerment as pointed out by Tamunomiebi and Chika-Anyanwu (2020). It has been defined differently by different researchers. However, for the direction of the discussion of this paper, it is necessary to define empowerment. Therefore, before going into the detailed discussion on empowerment, one needs to understand the meaning of empowerment. In general, when people are looking for the meaning of a certain word, they open the dictionary. Thus, we need to find out the meaning of empowerment in the dictionaries. Merriam-Webster defines "empowerment" as "to give official authority or legal power to". The emphasis in this definition is giving or sharing official authority to someone to act on behalf of the one who gives the authority. This definition is made even clearer in the Cambridge Dictionary when it defines empowerment as "the process of giving a group of people more freedom or rights". This definition

emphasizes empowerment as giving freedom or rights to people to take care of themselves. These definitions suggest that the objective of empowerment is for people to exercise freedom. While Collins Dictionary defines empowerment as “the giving or delegation of power or authority; authorization” or “the giving of an ability; enablement or permission”. The focus of this definition is about empowerment as a delegation of authority and enablement. Lastly, the LEXICO dictionary defines it as “authority or power given to someone to do something”. The definition refers to empowerment as delegating power to someone to do something on behalf of the one who is giving the authority. This means that the one who gives the power trusts the other one who is given the power to act on his/her behalf. However, this concept still recognizes that though the authority has been given, the authority giver is still responsible when things go wrong.

As emphasized by the definitions offered in the dictionaries, empowerment is a process of giving power (Collins Dictionary, Merriam-Webster). What does it mean “giving power?” From the social relationship perspective theory (Liu, 2015) power can be understood within a social relationship which means that power exists in an asymmetric interdependent social relationship. The asymmetric interdependent social relationship requires that one cannot function without the other one allowing the other to function. As Bacharach & Lawler, (1980), Hinings, Hickson, Pennings, & Schneck, (1974), Kotter, (1979), Pfeffer, (1981) pointed out that power is used to describe perceived power or control that one has over the others. Magee, et.al (2008) as cited by Liu (2015) contended that power “represents the interdependent social function and the asymmetric control of resources and results in the context of a particular situation and social relations”. Asymmetric control of resources indicates that there is only one who is holding the resources that are needed by others to function. Therefore, the power in this concept is related to the holding of important resources which is needed by others. In this case, power means holding resources which is important to the organization and the work of employees. In other words, employees cannot perform their duties and responsibilities without the resources which are held by the superiors. So, the source of power is the individual's ability to provide important resources that are needed by the organization and employees to perform their job. From this perspective, empowerment means delegating authority to perform or decide on their own. The assumption is that employees have the resources such as the information, knowledge, and skills to perform their job, and therefore, they do not rely on their superiors to provide. In this context, given the employees' resources (capability), they are authorized by their superiors to conduct their job and to decide freely on their own without relying on the superior's specific direction or without being dictated by their higher-ups (Wolf, 2001).

Following the above concept, it is clear that empowerment is a relational construct. Social exchanges theorists such as Blau, (1964), Emerson, (1962), Homans, (1974), and Thibaut & Kelley, (1959), argue that power is a function of the dependence or interdependence of actors. In this regard, power exists when an individual's performance depends on what others do or on how others respond (Thibaut & Kelley, 1959). In this concept, power becomes asymmetric control over the other which means that when actor X depends more on actor Y than actor Y depends on actor X, and therefore, actor Y has more power over actor X. The source of power is the ability of an actor to provide resources that are very much needed by other actors to perform their functions. At the organizational level, the sources of power of an actor can be the office of the actor and on the interpersonal level, the sources of power can be the personal characteristics of the actor such as referent power, the expertise of the actor, and specialized knowledge of the actor (Bacharach & Lawler, 1980). Based on this concept, their basis of exercising power is their legal position or office and from which the actor has the coercive power (punishment), remunerative power (the control of material rewards), normative power (control of symbolic rewards and knowledge power (control of information) (Bacharach & Lawler, 1980; Etzioni, 1961; French & Raven, 1959).

Drawing the understanding of empowerment as a relational construct (Conger & Kanungo, 1988), then one can argue that empowerment is a process of sharing the power to the employees or subordinates (Conger & Kanungo, 1988). In the context of our investigation, the managers or administrators share their power to their employees and authorize them to do things on their own freely (Burke's (1986). Thus, from management perspectives, empowerment can mean delegation and decentralization of decision-making (Burke, 1986). However, Conger and Kanungo (1988) argued that delegating authority, decentralizing decision making, and participating in decision making do not adequately address the nature of empowerment issues because empowerment is not just simply a management practice but it is the realization of human basic needs.

Empowerment is also a motivational construct (Conger & Kanungo, 1988). Behavioral psychologist, McClelland (1975) has pointed out that human beings have an inner need for power. Deci (1975) refers to this inner need as an intrinsic need, the need that is residing deep inside a man that needs to be realized/fulfilled. Human beings have an inner need to influence and control other people. On the one hand, this intrinsic need can be fulfilled when they feel that they have the power and when they can confront the events, situations, and people that challenge them. On the other hand, they feel powerless when they cannot confront those situations, events, and people that they face or when they cannot control their social environment. In this context, empowerment is not just a delegation of authority but implies motivating people through enablement. People must be enabled to control their environment by improving their self-efficacy (Conger & Kanungo, 1988). Therefore, along with such a concept, Conger and Kanungo (1988) suggest that empowerment should be viewed as a motivational construct because it is a strategy of enabling employees through the development of their efficacy. Thus, Conger and Kanungo define empowerment as " a process of enhancing feelings of self-efficacy among organizational members through the identification of conditions that foster powerlessness and through their removal by both formal organizational practices and informal techniques of providing efficacy". Thus, they recommended further that removing conditions that create powerlessness is important for empowerment and provide employees with self-efficacy information. Bandura (1994)

defines self-efficacy as “people’s beliefs about their capabilities to produce designated levels of performance that exercise their influence over events that affect their lives” (Bandura, 1994).

For the sake of our investigation and in line with the concept of empowerment as a relational construct and a motivational construct, therefore, the paper adopts delegation of authority, autonomy, and self-efficacy strategies as variables to be investigated. Empowering employees through enhancing their self-efficacy can be done through self-management. Chowdhury (2021), a certified psychiatric counselor has suggested that one of the ways to enhance self-efficacy is self-management. In self-management practices, the employees are given specific goals to be achieved. It is assumed that employees have the knowledge, skills, and experience when they apply for a job and after some years in the job, therefore, it is assumed that they can perform their job. However, when they are not clear with the direction of the company, are not clear with vision-mission and objective of the company, they can be demotivated to perform their job. Removing the conditions of powerlessness (Conger & Kanungo, 1988) and enhancing self-efficacy are ways of empowering employees. Information sharing is one way of removing the feeling of powerlessness and enhancing personal self-efficacy. Thus, it is important for management to involve the employees in crafting the vision and mission, and objective of the company for them to understand the direction of the company and be motivated to perform their functions. Employees also feel empowered when they are given the authority to decide on behalf of the supervisor and do their job autonomously (Abun, et.al (2021).

Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Organizational success is always attributed to the employees and therefore, the function of management is to improve the organizational performance through individual work performance such as task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive behavior (Koopmans, et.al.2011). However, determining factors or elements that cause individual work performance may not be easy. There can be a lot of factors or dimensions that cause job performance or work performance but one dimension that has been considered as a factor to influence work performance is the organizational citizenship behavior as found by the study of Mallick, et.al (2015), Basu, et.al (2017), Yaakobi and Weisberg (2020), Al-Mahasneh (2015). The discussion related to organizational citizenship behavior is nothing new because based on the historical investigation of Ocampo, et.al (2018) about the beginning discussion on organizational citizenship behavior has started as early as the 1930s. However, it was only officially defined in the 1980s and it seems that field study related to the topic was rather slow (Ocampo, et.al, 2018). Organizational citizenship behavior is defined by Mallick, et.al (2015) as “actions or behaviors that employees are willing to engage beyond their recommended role requirements”. They are good behaviors performed by employees voluntarily to help the organization. Organ (2015) defines it as “discretionary, nonrequired contributions by members to the organizations that employ them”. Al-Mahasneh (2015) argued that these are positive and constructive behavior that employees extend to help the organization and to help other employees beyond their job description. Along with this concept, organizational citizenship behavior or OCB has been classified into two kinds of behaviors which are behaviors that are directed to the organization (OCBO) and the individuals/persons (OCI/P) (Newland, 2012). These definitions help us to understand that not all employees have these kinds of behaviors. Some employees are coming to the workplace to complete the required number of hours and only perform the tasks that are emanated from the job description, but some employees exert extra effort voluntarily to make the organization better and make the work environment better (Borman, 2004). Examples would be volunteering extra work, cooperating with colleagues, and sharing ideas to help others (Newland, 2012). They are not demanding recognition such as incentives or praises from the management but they just do it for the sake of the organization.

The reasons why employees behave in a particular way may vary from one employee to another employee. The reasons can be related to their motivations. One person performs extra tasks because he/she wants to be seen as a nice employee but others perform organizational citizenship behavior because they want to help and not for recognition. Motivation has been defined as a “driving force that stimulates positive behavior at work and the tendency to remain committed” (Bartol & Martin, 1998). Farhad et al. (2011) argue that it is a motivation that moves us from boredom to interest. as Bartol and Martin (1998) contended that motivation is a force that inspires behaviors and maintains the persistent behavior to achieve the objectives. As Cherry (2020) contends that motivation is the one that maintains goal-oriented behaviors. Experts on organizational behavior argue that organizational citizenship develops due to motivation (Ariani, 2012; Davila & Finkelstein, 2013) and previous studies on motivation and OCB had established a correlation between the two variables (Allen and Rush, 1998, Organ (1998) and a meta-analysis (LePine, Erez and Johnson, 2002). However, we can also state that the motivation behind these voluntary behaviors may vary from one person to another person. Other people or employees pursue other activities that benefit the organization and other employees because of the working environment. A pleasant work environment motivates them to perform other non-required tasks to improve the organization (Ahmed & Khan, 2016). But others may pursue OCB because they want to get a good impression and to realize their pro-social values and show their concern to the organization (Newland, 2012). Some studies also showed that there is no correlation between extrinsic motivation and organizational citizenship behaviors (Barbuto and Scholl, 1999; Barbuto et al., 2000) and other studies also found a correlation between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation and organizational citizenship behavior ((Ibrahim & Aslinda, 2014). This was already pointed out by the study of Organ (1997) that future rewards motivated employees to exercise organizational citizenship behaviors. However, Ahmed and Khan (2016) argued that intrinsic and extrinsic motivation affects organizational citizenship behavior as long as the mediating factors such as job satisfaction, psychological empowerment, and organizational support are satisfied.

The above studies prove that organizational citizenship behaviors are motivated intrinsically as pointed out by Barbuto and Scholl, (1999), Barbuto et al. (2000), Ibrahim & Aslinda, (2014). There is a significant relationship between intrinsic motivation and

organizational citizenship behaviors but no significant relationship between external motivation and organizational citizenship behaviors. However, the relationship between motivation and OCB is not a straight path because mediating factors such as working environment, psychological empowerment, working relationship, and job satisfaction must be satisfied.

Empirical Review and Hypothesis Development

The Crucial Importance of Empowerment for Organizational Performance

The practices of empowerment have been done since the 1970s (Calves, 2009). Originally the word empowerment appeared in the English-speaking country and applied to social workers, public health workers, and community development (Simon 1994). Nowadays, the words have become popular and have entered the world of politics and business. The term was inspired by the feminist movement, Freudian Psychology, theology, the Black Power Movement, and Gandhism (Simon, 1994). Thus, the term was understood within those contexts which means empowerment as enabling a group and individuals to act on their own to ensure their well-being and their right to participate in decision making (Brock, et. al,2001). The term was anchored on the philosophy that gives priority to the powerless such as the oppressed and the marginalized to express themselves which leads them to gain power and overcome the domination (Wise, 2005). According to Wise (2005) empowerment has been practiced by the social workers in their work to empower themselves and others. Thus, based on the history of empowerment, the purpose of empowerment is to improve life, the well-being. However, since the practice of empowerment has shifted to the business organization, therefore, the purpose of empowerment is not limited to improving the life and well-being of a person but the life of the organization as a whole. This has been the concern of human resources management managers. The human resources managers have been looking for ways how to improve productivity, job satisfaction, work engagement, work performance, and organizational citizenship behavior and reduce counterproductive work behavior that damages the organization. There have been practices adopted by the human resource managers to increase the work performance of employees which include different practices of motivation, job appraisals, job satisfaction, training and development, benefits, salary, and promotion. Based on the related literature review, empowerment has been recognized as one of the effective strategies to improve individual and organizational performance (Tamunomiebi & Chika-Anyanwu, 2020). Wang and Zhang (2016) argued that improving job satisfaction and creativity can be done through psychological empowerment. Fardin (2012) opined that organizational effectiveness and flexibility are associated with empowerment practices. Abraiz & Raja (2012) pointed out several practices of empowerment that may improve performance such as assigning responsibility and accountability, sharing information and independence, encouraging creativity, initiative, and innovation, and participating in the decision-making process. The study of Raub & Robert (2010) strengthens the idea that job satisfaction, managerial effectiveness and creativity, and team performance are influenced by empowerment. They pointed out that giving the workers control, authority, power, and discretion over their job affect job satisfaction and work performance.

Measuring organizational performance has been taken from different dimensions which reflects its multidimensional construct. It depends on how the researchers understand organizational performance. Consequently, a different approach will result in different measures. Richard, et.al (2009) argued the problem occurs because of multiple definitions of performance and inconsistency of research methodology the researchers use in the investigation. For example, others measure organizational performance in terms of financial performance which is translated into value creation for the stockholders (Tamunomiebi & Chika-Anyanwu, 2020). Their measurement of organizational performance in terms of financial performance can be based on the stakeholders' theory of organizational performance. However, others measure organizational performance from both financial and nonfinancial variables performance ((Malina & Selto, 2004). Danielson and Press (2003) argued that a common measure that is being used in determining organizational performance is accounting measure or financial performance. However, the argument of Malina and Selto (2004) about non-financial performance measure of organizational performance can be applied to measure the organizational performance of education institutions because the performance is not measured by financial gains but the quality of outputs which is often measured in terms of percentage of professional licensure examination results.

Whatever the debate on the measurement of organizational performance, the focus of this paper is that empowerment affects the organizational citizenship behaviors of employees. Organizational citizenship behaviors influence organizational performance as a whole. Organizational performance is a sum-up of individual performance. Studies have shown that these individual performances are caused by the organizational citizenship behavior of employees which is associated with empowerment practices. Thus, the concern of the management is to find strategies on how to empower the employees.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual framework; *Source:* Abun, et.al (2021) and Fox and Specter (n.d).

The conceptual framework reflects the relationship between empowerment in terms of delegation of authority and self-efficacy and organizational citizenship behavior of employees in terms of OCBP and OCBO.

Hypothesis

The research found that when employees are empowered by the management, they feel empowered and when they feel empowered, they improve their performance, job satisfaction, and commitment to the organization (Seibert, et.al, 2011). Based on this finding, the study also hypothesized that when the employees feel empowered, they develop organizational citizenship behavior toward the organization and toward co-workers.

Research & Methodology

Scientific research requires following a specific method of investigation or research methodology. Research methodology is an established process for conducting the inquiry. It applies certain methods to determine, select, and analyze the data related to the concerned topic (Wilkinson, 2000, Leedy, 1974). Therefore, the current study applies certain methods of investigation such as research design, data gathering instruments method, the population of the study, the locale of the study, data gathering procedures, and the statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

The research design of the study is the descriptive assessment and descriptive correlational research design. Ariola (2006) argued that a descriptive correlation study is intended to describe the relationship among variables without seeking to establish a causal connection. While descriptive research is simply to describe a population, a situation, or a phenomenon. It is also used to describe profiles, frequency distribution, describe characteristics of people, situations, or phenomena. In short, it answers the question of what, when, how, where, and not why question (McCombes, 2020).

The locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word College of Laoag. The college is located in Laoag City, the capital of Ilocos Norte.

Population

The respondents of the study are the employees of the college. Since the number of employees is limited, therefore, the total enumeration sampling was used and thus all faculty and employees from the college were taken as respondents of the study.

Data Gathering instruments & procedures

The study adopted validated questionnaires of Abun, et.al. (2021) on employee empowerment, Fox and Specter (n.d) on organizational citizenship behavior. The questionnaires that are taken from Fox and Specter (n.d) are only those that are related to measuring the acts to help co-workers with job-related and the acts that are helping the organization which is classified as OCBO and OCBP.

To preserve the integrity of scientific research, the data were gathered after the approval of the President of the college. The researcher sent a letter to the president and after the letters were approved, the questionnaires were distributed by the researcher's representative. Then the researcher's representative from each institution collected the data and submitted it to the researcher for tabulation.

Ethical Procedures

The study was carried out after the research ethics committee examined and approved the content of the paper if it does not violate ethical standards and if it does not cause harm to human life and the environment.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To analyze the data, descriptive and inferential statistic was used. The weighted mean was used to determine the level of employee empowerment and organizational citizenship behavior of employees, and the Pearson r was used to measure the correlation between employee empowerment and organizational citizenship behavior of employees. The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

<i>Statistical Range</i>	<i>Descriptive Interpretation</i>
4.21-5.00	<i>strongly agree/ Very High</i>
3.41-4.20	<i>Agree / High</i>
2.61-3.40	<i>somewhat agree/ Moderate</i>
1.81-2.60	<i>Disagree/Low</i>
1.00-1.80	<i>Strongly disagree/Very Low</i>

Data Presentation and Analysis

As required by scientific research, a study must follow research methodology and be supported by data. This part presents data that were gathered through the research questionnaires. The presentation follows the statement of the problems of the study.

Problem 1: What is the employee empowerment of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of Delegation of authority, Autonomy/Independence, Self-Efficacy-Self-Management?

Table 1: Employee empowerment practices of Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of Delegation of Authority (n=172)

Indicators	Mean	DR
Employees are given the authority to decide on issues related to their work	3.56	A/H
Employees are given the authority to determine the course of action to accomplish the assigned task	3.58	A/H
The management clearly defines responsibilities and accountability procedures	3.62	A/H
Employees are allowed to take initiative to solve problems without the direction of their superiors	3.60	A/H
When the employees are delegated to do a certain task, they are given easy access to the resources needed to accomplish the task	3.63	A/H
The delegated person knows that he/she is accountable to the person who gives him/her the authority	3.66	A/H
All employees know what is expected of them in order of priority	3.63	A/H
Composite Mean	3.62	A/H

Source: Abun, et.al (2021).

Based on the data presented in the table, it reveals that as a whole the employee empowerment practices of the Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of delegation of authority gained a composite mean of 3.62 which is described as “agree/high”. This composite mean indicates that the empowerment practice of the Divine Word College of Laoag is not very high and it is also not very low, low, or moderate but it is high. This suggests that the employees agree that they are given a certain amount of authority to decide on behalf of their supervisors related to issues of their work, take initiative to solve problems on their own, and the management has defined their duties and responsibilities as guides for their actions.

Table 2: Employee empowerment practices of Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of Autonomy/Independence (n=172)

Indicators	Mean	DR
The management allows the employees to perform their work on their own based on what they know best without management’s intervention	3.63	A/H
The management encourages self-thinking and creativity at work	3.60	A/H
The management does not intervene too much in the work of employees	3.50	A/H
The management motivates employees to determine or to govern themselves	3.62	A/H
The employees are allowed to make their own decisions related to the work-related problems	3.66	A/H
The management appreciates ideas and recognizes employees’ effort	3.63	A/H
The employees are given easy access to the institution’s resources to perform their job	3.68	A/H
The management minimizes supervision and control on the work of an employee	3.62	A/H
Composite Mean	3.62	A/H

Source: Abun, et.al (2021)

As demonstrated by the data on the table, it appears that as a whole the empowerment practices of the Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of autonomy or independence obtained a composite mean rating of 3.62 which is considered "agree/high". This rating signifies that the empowerment practice of the Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of employees' autonomy is not very high and it is also not very low, low, or moderate but it is high. This shows that the employees agree that they are allowed to perform their tasks based on what they know best and make their own decision related to the issues of their work. They also agree that the management encourages self-thinking and creativity, does not intervene too much in their work, motivates them to govern themselves, recognizes ideas and efforts, minimizes supervision and control, and gives access to the institution's resources to facilitate their work.

Table 3: Employee empowerment practices of Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of Self-Efficacy Self-Management (n= 172)

Indicators	Mean	DR
Employees are invited and involved in creating the vision and mission of the organization	3.70	A/H
The individual employee determines their objective to accomplish	3.70	A/H
The employees organize their work based on the objectives	3.76	A/H
The employees are allowed to plan their work to achieve the vision and mission	3.66	A/H
Encourage employees to initiate activities in line with the vision-mission	3.66	A/H
Employees are allowed to make decisions based on the vision and mission	3.62	A/H
There is a regular assessment of the work together with the employees in line with the vision and mission	3.66	A/H
Composite Mean	3.68	

Source: Abun, et.al (2021).

As indicated by the data, it demonstrates that as a whole, the empowerment practice of the Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of self-efficacy self-management received a composite mean rating of 3.68 which is interpreted as "agree/high". This rating points out that as a whole the empowerment practice of the Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of self-efficacy self-management is not very high, and it is also not very low, low, or moderate but it is high. This suggests that the employees agree that they are invited to write the vision and mission of the organization as a direction of their work, allowed to set their objectives to be accomplished, allowed to plan their work to achieve the vision and mission, allowed to make decisions in line with the vision and mission, and assess the result of the work in line with the vision and mission.

Table 4: Summary of the employee empowerment practices of Divine Word College of Laoag (n = 172)

Empowerment Practices	Mean	DR
Delegation of Authority	3.62	A/H
Autonomy/Independence	3.62	A/H
Self-Efficacy Self-Management	3.68	A/H
Overall Mean	3.64	A/H

The data on the summary table reveals that overall the empowerment practices of the Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of the three dimensions measured by this study obtained an overall mean rating of 3.64 which is described as "agree/high". This rating concludes that the empowerment practice of Divine Word College of Laoag is not very high and it is not also very low, low, or moderate but it is high. In this regard. the employees agree that the management practice a certain level of empowerment specifically in terms of delegation of authority, autonomy, and self-efficacy self-management.

Problem 2: What is the organizational citizenship behavior of employees in terms of OCBP & OCBO?

Table 5: Organizational citizenship behavior of employees of Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of OCBP

Indicators	Mean	DR
Lent a compassionate ear when someone had a work problem	3.70	A/H
Lent a compassionate ear when someone had a personal problem	3.66	A/H
Change vacation schedule, workdays, or shifts to accommodate co-workers' needs	3.66	A/H
Help a less capable co-worker lift a heavy box or other objects	3.66	A/H
Went out of the way to encourage co-workers or express appreciation	3.71	A/H
Defended co-worker who was being 'put down' or spoken ill by other co-workers or supervisors	3.72	A/H
Help co-workers with personal matters such as sharing food or drinks	3.61	A/H
Lent money or personal property to a co-worker	3.64	A/H
Composite Mean	3.67	A/H

Source: Fox and Spector (n.d).

Based on the data presented in the table, it displays that as a whole the organizational citizenship behavior of the employees of the Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of OCBP or organizational citizenship behavior toward people obtained a composite mean of 3.67 which means "agree/high". This composite mean signifies that the organizational citizenship behavior of the employees in terms of OCBP or organizational citizenship behavior toward people/coworkers is not very high and it is also not very low, low, or moderate but it is high. This suggests that the organizational citizenship behavior of employees toward their coworkers is high but not very high. The employees agree that they lent a compassionate ear to their fellow employees who had personal or work-related problems, help other employees who had difficulties in carrying out their tasks and help other employees who have financial and food problems. They also agree that they sacrificed their time to help other employees, went out of their ways to encourage someone who had problems, and defend other employees who were put down by the other employees or superiors.

Table 6: Organizational citizenship behavior of employees of Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of OCBO

Indicators	Mean	DR
Help new employees get oriented to the job	3.62	A/H
Offered suggestions to improve how work is done	3.62	A/H
Volunteered for extra work assignments	3.66	A/H
Volunteered for extra work assignments that are required for the benefits of the organization	3.65	A/H
Said good things about your school in the community outside the school	3.64	A/H
Give up meals and other breaks to complete the work	3.62	A/H
Offered suggestions for improving the work environment	3.66	A/H
Come in early or stay late without pay to complete a project or task	3.70	A/H
Volunteer to share new job knowledge or skills with other employees	3.67	A/H
Composite Mean	3.65	A/H

Source: Fox and Spector (n.d).

As shown by the data on the table, it manifests that as a whole the organizational citizenship behavior of the employees of the Divine Word College of Laoag in terms of OCBO or organizational citizenship behavior toward the organization gained a composite mean of 3.65 which is interpreted as "agree/high". This mean rating implies that as a whole the organizational citizenship behavior of employees in terms of OCBO is not very high and it is also not very low, low, or moderate but it is high. It suggests that the employees' organizational citizenship behavior of employees toward the organization is high. They agree that they help other employees to get oriented in their job, suggest other employees on how to perform their tasks and to improve the work environment, volunteer to perform extra work to help the organization, say good things about the school community with other people outside the school, come in early or stay late to complete the work and volunteer to share job knowledge or skills with other employees.

Table 7: Summary of the organizational citizenship behavior of employees of Divine Word College of Laoag

Organizational Citizenship Behavior	Mean	DR
OCBP	3.67	A/H
OCBO	3.65	A/H
Overall Mean	3.66	A/H

The summary table reveals that overall the organizational citizenship behavior of employees of Divine Word College of Laoag is high with an overall mean of 3.66. Even when they are taken singly, it shows that their organizational citizenship behavior in terms of OCBP and OCBO is also high with the composite mean rating of 3.67 and 3.65 respectively. They agree that they extend extra effort to help other employees and the organization beyond their job description.

Problem 3: Is there a relationship between empowerment practices and OCBP and OCBO?

Empowerment Practices and OCBP

Table 8: Model SummaryModel

	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.809 ^a	.655	.653		.43870
2	.822 ^b	.675	.671		.42692

a. predictors: (constant), autonomy/independence

b. predictors: (constant), autonomy/independence, delegation of authority

Source: IBM SPSS Software

Table 9: Anova^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	64.680	3	21.560	120.069	.000 ^b
	Residual	30.167	168	.180		
	Total	94.847	171			

a. Dependent Variable: OCBP

b. Predictors: (Constant), Delegation of Authority, Self-efficacy-Self-management, Autonomy/Independence.

Source: IBM SPSS Software

Table 10: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	.727		4.474	.000
	Self-efficacy and self-management	.160	.173	1.881	.062
	Autonomy/independence	.393	.396	3.332	.001
	Delegation of authority	.258	.288	2.452	.015

a. Dependent Variable: OCBP

Source: IBM SPSS Software

As indicated by the coefficient correlation table, it shows that the empowerment practices such as delegation of authority, autonomy/independence, and self-efficacy self-management when taken together significantly predicted the OCBP of the respondents, $F(3,168) = 120.069$ $p < .01$ with 80% overlap between the three predictors and the outcome of the OCBP. Specifically, the employment practices of autonomy/independence $B = .393$ $p = .000$ and delegation of authority $B = .258$ $p = .015$. $.727$ quantified the Y-intercept for the regression equation.

In other words, the empowerment practices of delegation of authority, autonomy/independence, and self-efficacy self-management when taken together could predict the OCBP of the respondents. However, when the empowerment practices are considered singly it was the only delegation of authority and autonomy/independence which could predict OCBP of the respondents.

Empowerment Practices and OCBO

Table 11: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.848 ^a	.719	.714	.40457

Source: SPSS Software

a. Predictors: (Constant), the delegation of authority, Self-efficacy management, Autonomy /independence

Table 12: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	70.271	3	23.424	143.112	.000 ^b
	Residual	27.497	168	.164		
	Total	97.768	171			

a. Dependent Variable: OCBO

b. Predictors: (Constant), Delegation Of Authority, Self-Efficacy And Self-Management, Autonomy/Independence

Source: IBM SPSS Software

Table 13: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	.642		4.141	.000
	Self-efficacy and self-management	.039	.042	.484	.629
	Autonomy/independence	.392	.389	3.481	.001
	Delegation of authority	.400	.439	3.979	.000

a. Dependent Variable: OCBO

Source: IBM SPSS Software

Based on the coefficient correlation table, it demonstrates that the empowerment practices such as delegation of authority, autonomy/independence, and self-efficacy self-management if taken together significantly predicted the OCBO of the respondents, $F(3,168) = 143.112$ $p < .01$ with 84% between the three predictors and the outcome of OCBO. Specifically, the employment practice of autonomy/independence $B = .392$; $p = .001$; and delegation of authority $B = .400$; $p = .000$; $.642$ quantified the Y-intercept for the regression equation.

In other words, the empowerment practices of delegation of authority, autonomy/independence, and self-efficacy self-management considered together could predict the OCBO of the respondents. However, when the empowerment practices are considered singly it was only autonomy/independence and delegation of authority that could predict the OCBO of the respondents.

Result and Discussion

Strategies on how to Motivate employees to love their organization and love their work have no simple solution or simple formula. One of the objectives of the management is for the employees to love their organization and their work. Because we all believe that when one loves his organization and his work, it will boil down to self-sacrifice for the organization, the work, and other employees. However, though it has no right formula to achieve such an objective the management needs to find ways to motivate employees to love their organization and their work because organizational success depends on it. There have been a lot of studies about the effect of organizational citizenship behavior on job performance, organizational performance or success, work quality, creativity. For example, the study of Sadeghi, et.al (2016), Yaakobi and Weisberg (2020), Mallick, et.al (2015), Basu, et.al (2017), Mahfudz, et.al (2019), Andrew and Cazarez (2015). All these studies pointed out the same result that organizational citizenship behaviors help the organization achieves its objectives.

The result of those studies should be a clear reminder for the managers of any organization, that finding strategies on how to motivate employees to develop organizational citizenship behavior of employees toward the organization, the work, and toward the coworkers are a primary concern. The result of the current study suggests that empowerment is one of the strategies that the management can apply. Delegation of authority, employee autonomy, and self-efficacy self-management can be used to motivate employees to develop their organizational citizenship behaviors. Delegation of authority is a motivation strategy to enhance the leadership capability of the employees. Allowing employees autonomy can develop self-confidence in employees to perform their job on their own without strict supervision from the supervisors. Self-efficacy self-management motivates employees to develop self-efficacy by allowing them to manage their work. Based on the current result of the study, specific attention must be given to autonomy and delegation of authority as the very important elements in promoting organizational citizenship behavior of the employees.

Conclusion

The study aimed to determine the effect of empowerment practice of the Divine Word College of Laoag on the organizational citizenship behavior of the employees particularly their organizational citizenship behavior toward the coworkers and the organization. The study found that the empowerment practices of the institution are considered high and their organizational citizenship behavior is also high. In terms of the relationship between empowerment practices and organizational citizenship behavior, it was found to be significantly correlated.

The finding of this study answers the hypothesis of the study that there is a correlation between empowerment practices and organizational citizenship behavior and therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. The management needs to give special attention to empowerment strategies particularly delegation of authority, autonomy, and self-efficacy self-management.

Acknowledgement

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, D.A, T.M., V.G.C., M.F.J., FP.J.; methodology, D.A, T.M., V.G.C., M.F.J., FP.J.; Data Collection, D.A, T.M., V.G.C., M.F.J., FP.J.; formal analysis, D.A, T.M., V.G.C., M.F.J., FP.J.; writing—original draft preparation, D.A, T.M., V.G.C., M.F.J., FP.J.; writing—review and editing, D.A, T.M., V.G.C., M.F.J., FP.J.; All authors have read and agreed to the published the final version of the manuscript.

Institutional Review Board Statement: The study was carried out after the research ethics committee examined and approved the content of the paper if it does not violate ethical standards and if it does not cause harm to human life and the environment.

Data Availability Statement: The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- Abraiz, A. R. & Sobia (2012). *Empowerment effects and employees' job satisfaction*. Academic Research International, 3(3).
- Abun, D. Basilio, G.J.Q., Magallanes, T., Encarnacion, M.J. & Sallong, M. (2021). *Examining the link between organizational citizenship behavior and work performance of employees in the private schools, mediated by the workplace environment*. International Journal of Research in Business & Social Science, 10(4), 85-98.
- Abun, D., Luca, M.O., Magallanes, T., Encarnacion, M.J. & Flores, N. (2021). *Empowering Leadership of the Heads as Perceived by the Employees and Employees' Job Satisfaction*. Technium Social Science Journal, 17, 398-423.
- Ahmed, S.W. & Khan, T. (2016). *Does Motivation Lead to Organizational Citizenship Behavior: A Theoretical Review*. Global Journal of Management and Business Research: Administration and Management, 16(7).
- Allen, T. D., & Rush, M. C. (1998). *The effects of organizational citizenship behavior on performance judgments: A field study and a laboratory experiment*. Journal of Applied Psychology, 83, 247– 260.

- Al-Mahasneh, M.A. (2015). *The impact of Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Job Performance at Greater Amman Municipality*. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7(36).
- Ariani, Dorothea W. (2012). *Comparing motives of organizational citizenship behavior between academic staffs' universities and teller staffs' banks in Indonesia*. *International Journal of Business and Management*, Vol.7, No.1.
- Ariola, M.M. (2006). *Principles and Methods of Research*. Manila: Rex Book Store
- Bacharach, S. B., & Lawler, E. J. (1980). *Power and politics in organizations*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Barbuto, J. E., & Scholl, R. W. (1999). *Leaders' motivation and perception of followers' motivation as predictors of influence tactics used*. *Psychological Reports*, 84, 1087-1098
- Barbuto, J. E., Fritz, S. M., & Marx, D. (2000). *A field study of two measures of work motivation for predicting leaders' transformational behavior*. *Psychological Reports*, 86, 295-300.
- Bartol, K.M. and Martin, D.C. (Ed.). (1998). *Management (3rd)*. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill
- Basu, E., Pradhan, R.K., Tewari, H.R. (2017). *Impact of organizational citizenship behavior on job performance in Indian healthcare industries: The mediating role of social capital*. *International Journal of Prod. and Performance Man*, 66(6).
- Blau, P. M. (1964). *Exchange and power in social life*. New York: Wiley
- Borman, W.C. (2004). *The concept of organizational citizenship*. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 13, 238-241. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.13.1.70>.
- Brock, K., Cornwall, A. & Gaventa, J. (2001). *Power, Knowledge and Political Spaces in the Framing of Poverty Policy*. IDS Working Paper 143, Institute of Development Studies, Brighton
- Burke, W. (1986). *Leadership is empowering others*. In S. Srivastara (Ed.), *Executive power* (pp. 51-77). San Fra.: Jossey-Bass.
- Callaway, P. H. (2007). *The relationship between organizational trust and job satisfaction: an analysis in the U.S. Federal Workforce*. Retrieved from <http://www.dissertation.com>
- Calvès, A. (2009). *Empowerment: The History of a Key Concept in Contemporary Development Discourse*. *Revue Tiers Monde*, 200, 735-749. <https://doi.org/10.3917/rtm.200.0735>
- Cherry, K. (2020). *What is Motivation?* Very Well Mind. Retrieved from <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-motivation-2795378>
- Chowdhury, M.R. (2021). *Four Ways to Improve and Increase Self-Efficacy*. *Positive Psychology*. Retrieved from <https://positivepsychology.com/3-ways-build-self-efficacy/>
- Conger, J.A. & Kanungo, R.N. (1988). *The Empowerment Process: Integrating Theory and Practice*. *Academy of Management Review*, 13(3), 471-482.
- Davila, M. C. & Finkelstein, M. A. (2013). *Organizational Citizenship behavior and well-being: preliminary results*. *International Journal of Applied Psychology*, 3(3), 45-51.
- Deci, E. L. (1975). *Intrinsic motivation*. New York: Plenum
- Emerson, R. M. (1962). *Power-dependence relations*. *American Sociological Review*, 27, 31-41
- Etzioni, A. (1961). *A comparative analysis of complex organizations*. New York: Free Press.
- Fard, P.G. & Karimi, F. (2015). *The Relationship between Organizational Trust and Organizational Silence with Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment of the Employees of University*. *International Education Studies*; 8(11).
- Fardin, H. G.H. (2012). *Evaluation of empowerment of human resources and effectiveness*. *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*, 2(10)9998-10006.
- Farhad, J. L., Zhong, C. B., & Organ, D. W. (2011). *Organizational citizenship behavior in the People's Republic of China*. *Organization Science*, 15, 241– 253.
- Fox, S., Spector, P. E., Goh, A., Bruursema, K., & Kessler, S. R. (2009). *The deviant citizen: Clarifying the measurement of organizational citizenship behavior and its relation to counterproductive work behavior*. Chicago: Loyola University Press
- French, J., Jr., & Raven, B. (1959). *The basis of social power*. In D. Cartwright (Ed.), *Studies in social power* (pp. 150-167). University of Michigan: Institute for Social Research
- Gucer, E. & Demirdag, S.A. (2014). *Organizational Trust and Job Satisfaction: A Study on Hotels*. *Business Management Dynamics*, 4(1), 12-28.
- Herselman, S. (2003). *A Little Bit of Distrust: Causes and Consequences of the Trust Gap for Work Performance and a Relationship in a Wholesale Company*. *Anthropology Southern Africa*, 26(3&4).
- Hinings, C. R., Hickson, D. J., Pennings, J. M., & Schneck, R. E. (1974). *Conditions of intra-organizational power*. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 14, 378-397.
- Homans, A. (1974). *Social behavior: Its elementary forms*. New York: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich
- Kanter, R. M. (1979). *Power failure in management circuits*. *Harvard Business Review*, 57(4), 65-75.
- Koopmans, L., Bernaards, C., Hildebrandt, V. & Van der Beek, A.J. (2011). *Conceptual Frameworks of Individual Work Performance*. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine* 53(8):856-66
- Leedy, P.D. (1974). *Practical research: planning and design*. New York: Macmillan
- Liu, Y. (2015). *The Review of Empowerment Leadership*. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 3, 476-482.
- LePine, J. A., Erez, A., & Johnson, D. E. (2002). *The nature and dimensionality of organizational citizenship behavior: A critical review and meta-analysis*. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87(1), 52- 65.
- Liu, Y. (2015). *The Review of Empowerment Leadership*. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 3, 476-482.

- Mahfudz, M., Sukresna, M., & Laksana, R.D. & Shaferi, I. (2019). *Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Public Organizational Performance*. Journal of International Proceedings, 2(3).
- Mallick, E., Pradhan, R.K., & Tewari, H.R. (2015). *Organizational Citizenship Behaviour, Job Performance, and HR Practices: A Relational Perspective*. Management and Labor Studies, 39(4). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0258042X15578023>
- Malina, M. A., & Seto, F. H. (2004). *Choice and change of measures in performance measurement models*. Management Accounting Research, 15: 441–469.
- Mallick, E., Pradhan, R. K., Tewari, H. R., & Jena, L. K. (2014). *Organizational Citizenship Behaviour, Job Performance, and HR Practices: A Relational Perspective*. Management and Labour Studies, 39(4), 449–460. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0258042X15578023>.
- McClelland, D. C. (1975). *Power: The inner experience*. New York: Irvington Press
- Thielsch, M. T., Meeßen, S. M., & Hertel, G. (2018). *Trust and distrust in information systems at the workplace*. PeerJ, 6, e5483. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.5483>
- Magee, J.C. (2008). *Power and the Objectification of Social Targets*. Journal of Personality & Social Psychology, 95, 111-127. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.95.1.111>
- McCombes, S. (2020). *Descriptive Research*. Scribbr. Retrieved from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/descriptive-research/>
- Newland, S. J. (2012). *Organizational Citizenship Behavior- Individual or Organizational Citizenship Behavior- Organization: Does the Underlying Motive Matter?* Masters Theses & Specialist Projects. Paper 1159. <http://digitalcommons.wku.edu/theses/1159>
- Ocampo, L., Acedillo, V., Bacunador, A.M. (2018). *A historical review of the development of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) and its implications for the twenty-first century*. Personnel Review 47(4):821-862
- Organ, D. W. (1988). *Organizational citizenship behavior: The good soldier syndrome*. USA: D.C. Heath and Company
- Organ, D.W. (2015). *Organizational Citizenship Behavior*. In *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences (Second Edition)*. Amsterdam: Elsevier.
- Ömer G. Mesut A. & Mehmet, T. (2019). *Organizational trust, employee commitment, and job satisfaction in Turkish hospitals: implications for public policy and health*. Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal, 25(9).
- Pfeffer, J. (1981). *Power in organizations*. Marshfield, MA: Pitman
- Raub, S., & Robert, C. (2010). *Differential effects of empowering leadership on in-role and extra-role employee behaviors: Exploring the role of psychological empowerment and power values*. Human Relations, 63(11), 1743–1770
- Podsakoff, P.M. & MacKenzie, S.B. (1997). *Impact of Organizational Citizenship Behavior on Organizational Performance: A Review and Suggestion for Future Research*. Human Performance, 10 (2), 133-151. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327043hup1002_5
- Richard, R., Yip, G., Devinney, T., & Johnson, G. (2009). *Measuring Organizational Performance: Toward Methodological Best Practices*. Journal of Management, 35(3), 718-814.
- Sadeghi, G., Ahmadi, M., & Yazdi, M.T. (2016). *The relationship between organizational citizenship behavior and organizational performance (case study: Agricultural Jihad Organization of Mazandaran Province)*. Problems and Perspectives in Management, 14(3).
- Seibert, S. E., Wang, G., & Courtright, S. H. (2011). *Antecedents and consequences of psychological and team empowerment in organizations: A meta-analytic review*. Journal of Applied Psychology, 96(5), 981–1003. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0022676>
- Simon, B. L. (1994). *The empowerment tradition in American social work: A history*. New York: Columbia University Press
- Tamunomiebi, M.D., Chika-Anyanwu. H. (2020). *Empowerment Practices and Organizational Performance: A Review of Literature*. International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science, 4(8).
- Thibault, J. W., & Kelley, H. H. (1959). *The social psychology of groups*. New York: Wiley
- Ugwu, F.O., Onyishi, I.E. and Rodríguez-Sánchez, A.M. (2014). *Linking organizational trust with employee engagement: the role of psychological empowerment*. Personnel Review, 43 (3), 377-400. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-11-2012-0198>
- Wang, F. & Zhang, H. (2016). *An Empirical Study on the influencing factors of university librarians' psychological capital*. Shandong Library Journal, 4, 10-16.
- Wilkinson, D. (2000). *The researcher's Toolkit: the complete guide to practitioner research*. New York: Routledge/Falmer
- Wise, J. B. (2005). *Empowerment Practice with Families in Distress*. New York Chichester, West Sussex: Columbia University Press. <https://doi.org/10.7312/wise12462>
- Wolf, P.J. (2001). *Authority: Delegation*. International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioural Sciences, 972-978. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B0.080430767044764>
- Yaakobi, E. & Weisberg, J. (2020). *Organizational Citizenship Behavior Predicts Quality, Creativity, and Efficiency Performance: The Roles of Occupational and Collective Efficacies*. Front. Psychol. 11:758. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00758>

Publisher's Note: Bussecon International stays neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

International Journal of Business Ecosystem and Strategy by [Bussecon International Academy](https://www.bussecon.com/) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).